

PRODUCT INNOVATIVENESS MODEL OF HERBAL BUSINESS IN RANONG, THAILAND

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Abstract

The usage of management accounting systems during the production process can help sectors and their managers in making decisions about the production process and also help them to achieve long term goals and objectives. This given research study explores the impact of environmental dynamism on the better product innovativeness and makes use of a management accounting system mainly during the making of drugs. This study also investigates the mediating impact of technological turbulence that can affect the level of using management accounting systems and the choice of brand innovativeness strategy. At the same time, the research also focuses on the moderating effect of locus of control in all relationships of the study. For this purpose, the data of the study were collected from about 471 employees of herbal organizations, in which 209 were female and 262 were male. The KMO, descriptive statistics and SEM are used to analyze data and also test the hypothesis. Almost all the results of the study showed that environmental dynamism has a significant relationship with other variables of the study. The outcomes of the given study positively contribute to the herbal sector of Thailand and help their managers to design a positive system of MAS.

Keywords: Environmental dynamism, product innovation, management accounting system, technological turbulence, locus of control

1. INTRODUCTION

In a current dynamic environment, there is a great change in the preferences level of the customers in the market(Coccia, 2018a). It is occurred due to the high enforcement of technology and innovation in the operating activities of the majority of the organizations (Coccia, 2018b). In this case, a herbal company plays a major role to upgrade the health drug-making process in its production houses. Many business persons are now adopting technological turbulence and the customer adoption level in order to maintain their position in the high competitive market(Farooq & Vij, 2017).

In this situation, an internal management system plays a major role to make a proper strategic approach of an organization to process the innovative products in the existing and new markets (Marangos & Warren, 2017). Due to the dynamic environmental nature, herbal companies' majority focused on making some stimulants, opium related painkillers, depressants and hallucinogens, by molding such drugs with an advanced technology (Spaans, 2019). In order to evaluate the direct impact of the customer purchasing level due to the changing environment, the following figures explore the current figures regarding customer demand in this health drug-making industry(Sansgiry, Bhansali, Bapat, & Xu, 2017; Kerdpitak, 2022). The pie-chart based representation of such current figures is below;

Figure 1: Global Drugs Market top Sub-segment shares

According to the above-mentioned figure, it becomes clear that the majority of the patients majorly demand antibiotics from the companies, while others want antiviral, anti-hypertensive and anti-asthmatics, while very few of them desire the anti-rheumatoid from the departmental and clinical stores (Volqvartz et al., 2019).

While the remaining 70% of the customers desire other types of drugs (Volqvartz et al., 2019). This shows that in the current era, the percentage of diseases among the customers is continuously changing due to the changing nature of the environment (Taylor, 2017). Those companies who focused on the technological development in their operating, manufacturing, selling and marketing activities, are more profitable and in a high rank. An innovation adoptive and perfect management accounting system based companies majorly focused on the following over the counter drugs.

Table 1: Market Shares of Over the Counter Drugs

Over the Counter Drugs	Market Shares (In Percentage)
Cough, Cold and Allergy Remedies	50
Digestive Remedies	34
Analgesics	26
Eye Care	20
Sleep Aids	19
Smoking Cessation Aids	28
Wound Care	24
Emergency Contraception	20
Other supplements	25

The above tables explored the current environment and customer preference based situation that the majority of the drugs and its related are directly based on the external stakeholder factors like customers, shareholders, competitors, government policies and other related factors (Bischoff, 2018). Such factors majorly impact the productivity factor of such health drug-making companies. Such enforcement of the external environment made a pressure on

the company to make some innovative, efficient and highly profitable products in the market which fulfils the customer's demand. In the current era, an excessive usage of technology plays a major role in front of the management to developing such policies that do not oppose the needs and desires of the customers (Volqvartz et al., 2019; Westermann-Clark, Pepper, & Lockey, 2018).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Environmental Dynamism and Product Innovativeness

A research was conducted by researchers in their journal, where they critically evaluate the impact of the innovativeness on the productivity and profit margin of a company (Zulu-Chisanga, Boso, Adeola, & Oghazi, 2016). According to the scholars, it is a basic necessity of a company in order to survive in a highly competitive market. The management must be quite efficient and capable to survive in the dynamic and adverse environment (Zheng & Yu, 2017). At this time, a network density act as a heterogeneous way by improving the impact of technology and market dynamics on the new ideas (Rodrigo-Alarcón, García-Villaverde, Parra-Requena, & Ruiz-Ortega, 2017). So the proposed hypothesis is given below;

H1: Environmental Dynamism has a significant direct impact on Product Innovativeness

2.2 Environmental Dynamism and MAS Use

Many researches are made to explore the influencing power of environmental dynamics on the management accounting system in the operating activities of a company (TAN, 2017). The relevant researches were conducted by George, Lestari and other researchers in 2019. According to the researchers, an external environment plays a major role to shape the behavioural perspective and culture within and outside the organization (Gregor, 2019; Lestari, Winata, & Mia, 2019). According to the scholars, the majority of the innovation projects are majorly based on fulfilling the needs and desires the targeted customers, or creating desires among the customers (Djerroud & Cherif, 2019). Hence, these studies suggested the following hypothesis;

H2: Environmental Dynamism has a significant direct impact on MAS Use

2.3 Mediating Role of Technological turbulence between environmental dynamism and Product Innovativeness

The technology turbulence has now become a real force which enforce a person to adopt advanced and innovative thing in his life (Martinez-Conesa, Soto-Acosta, & Carayannis, 2017). This enforcement level enhances the competition level, according to Djerroud with others in their research article (Djerroud & Cherif, 2019). Another research also explored the direct impact of the technology to make a dynamic environment and product innovation factor. According to researchers, such factors run a business and country's economy (Bodlaj & Čater, 2019; Djerroud & Cherif, 2019). Another one also highlights this point by relating it to the firm's productivity and profitability factor (Niazi, Ghani, & Aziz, 2019). According to them, it

generates a war of wealth among the companies, groups and even the states (Turulja & Bajgoric, 2019). So, the proposed hypothesis of this research is given below;

H3: Technological turbulence between Environmental Dynamism and Product Innovativeness

2.4 Mediating Role of Technological Turbulence between Environmental Dynamism and MAS Use

In case of the efficient management accounting system adoption, a research was conducted by different researchers, where they critically evaluate the impact of the technological war on the productivity factor of a business(Mao, Li, & Guo, 2020). According to them, this factor motivates the manager to upgrade his strategies and business model with the changing culture and makes some effective decision-making process to inspire the customers to purchase his product.

According to the researchers, the external environmental dynamics generate a culture and perception level of the customers and the company's management to follow the trends of the market (bin Zainuddin, 2017; Lin, Germain, & Krotov, 2019). This is a productive approach to shape the behavior of a market (Abidemi, Halim, & Alshuabi, 2017). Hence, after such constructive researches, a hypothesis is proposed which is given below;

H4: Technological turbulence has a significant mediating role between Environmental Dynamism and Product Innovativeness

2.5 Moderating role of internal locus of control between Technological Turbulence and Product Innovativeness

In order to explore the influencing role of the internal locus of control on an organizational productivity, a research was conducted by different scholars at this point(Wang, Quarr, & Tsai, 2018). According to them, both customers and companies try to make a control on the perception level of one another. Like, the majority of the companies make such strategies where they can easily make control on the behavioral perspective of a person(Ozdemir, Kandemir, Eng, & Gupta, 2019).

They also discussed different ways to help the company in order to cultivate the internal locus of control, like by identifying the goals and distribute them in different sectors. The second step is to turn a criticism into the growth of a company, like making some innovation and technological adventure in the working activities(Lyu, He, Zhu, & Li, 2019). After this, they discussed the importance of the support system in this case. So, such studies proposed the following hypothesis;

H5: Internal Locus of control has a significant moderating role between Technological Turbulence and Product Innovativeness

2.6 Moderating role of Internal Locus of control between technological turbulence and MAS Use

In a current human resource department, where it now becomes essential for a manager to critically observe and analyze a current situation of a workplace and customer preferences and then make effective policies in the business model (Orsatti, Quatraro, & Pezzoni, 2020). Many researchers justified this point in their researchers that the perceived level of a customer towards a company's services and product is much important in the current era. The researchers concluded that the majority of the companies makes some locus in the mind of the customers that they controlled the operations and other decision making process of a company (Sheng, 2017).

But in a real-world, organization shapes behavioral approach of customers. The majority of researchers justified this point that technological enforcement is basically made by a businessman who wants to earn more money by running the community in his own way (Orsatti et al., 2020; Sheng, 2017). They stated that the majority of the organizations make such statements in their marketing campaign which aim to retain the customers (Orsatti et al., 2020). So, the above studies proposed a following hypothesis;

H6: Internal Locus of control has a significant moderating role between Technological Turbulence and MAS Use

2.7 Theoretical framework

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Participants and Data

The current study was conducted in Thailand's herbal sector, fastest growing market and second largest herbal market in South-Asia, containing convenient sample of 471 workers from 20 herbal firms that are engaged in drugs making. These firms were targeted because they are disposed to rapid technological development and innovation. Information about the targeted firms was gathered through herbal Association of Thailand, those firms were selected that have strong market share and brand name. Convenient sampling technique was used to pick respondents who are familiar to the research topic. Online survey was conducted in 20 firms, to obtain data for survey. Self-administrative questionnaires' was distributed through email. Five hundred fifty questionnaires were sent with brief explanation about the research, through email only four hundred ten workers responded back. On data screening, 70 questionnaires were rejected due to incomplete and insufficient data and 471 were picked for statistical analysis. The majority of participants were male 55.6% having more than 2 to 5 years of experience in health service and aged between 25 to 35 years of age. Main sample respondents were managers (marketing, R&D and production) and supervisors who had understanding of variables.

3.2 Measurements

Different scales developed and confirmed by previous researchers were used to test Hypothetical Model Our questionnaire contains 28 items; each item was rate on five-point Likert scale.

Environmental dynamism is measured by 4 items adapted from Jaworski and Kohli (1993) scale. Four items including "the market competitive conditions were highly unpredictable and Customers 'product preferences changed quite rapidly'" to estimate the rate of change. Responses were noted on 5 Point-Likert scale ranging from 1=very slow to 5= very fast. Statistical finding showed $\alpha = 0.919$ composite reliability for environmental dynamism. For measuring product innovativeness of a firm, 3 items scale was selected. Three items were utilized to measure firm's capacity innovate their products such as "Most of our new products introduced in the past three years relied on technology which has never been used in the industry before". Responses were recorded on Five-point scale ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree with $\alpha = 0.931$ as CR. Internal Locus of control construct was evaluated by using Mueller and Thomas (2001). Ten items were taken and modified according to requirement of this study. One of these 10 items is "my success depends on whether I am lucky enough to be in the right place at the right time". Participants were acquired to rate locus of control on 5 scales ranging from 1= very weak to 5= very strong. Results yielded Cronbach alpha $\alpha = 0.923$. MAS information use was measured by ensuing Agbejule (2005) and Chenhall and Morris (1986) 4 items scale on Likert 5-points in terms of broad scope, integration, timeliness and aggregation in current questionnaire. Results showed $\alpha = 0.936$ as Cronbach alpha. Scale to validate Technological turbulence was Jaworski and Kohli (1993) , seven items were picked and altered , five items were used one sample item is "The technology in our firm is rapidly changing" and Cronbach's alpha for this construct was 0.949.

3.3 Analysis

The reliability of the constructs of our study is tested using confirmatory factor analysis (Hassan, Hameed, Basheer, & Ali, 2020; Iqbal & Hameed, 2020) and descriptive statistics on AMOS statistical software. There is no cross-loadings between the items of constructs in our model, and all factors loadings. Some measures were used to alleviate common method biases. AMOS has been used in this study to draw graphical models using simple drawing tools and quickly performing the valuation for different analysis and display the results.

4. RESULTS

Data for this study was obtained from a sample of 471 employees working in herbal firms in Thailand, sample characteristics shows that 262 males were dominating the sample that's majority of workers is male in these firms, Females also participated in the survey that were 209 in total. 149 participants were not more than 25 years of age with less than 2 years' experience, 204 aged up to 25 to 35 years with more than 2 years' experience in this sector. Responses that drawn from this sample were statistically analyzed to test the projected variable model. Results are illustrated below in form of table along with interpretation.

Table 1: KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.947
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	17812.985
	df	378
	Sig.	.000

KMO and Bartlett's Test is depicted in Table 1, that is used to check either sample is adequate or not. The value showed by test is .947 that is ranges between threshold values of 0.8 to 1 which confirms that selected sample is adequate and suitable. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity signposts the approximate of Chi-square as 17812.985 with 378 degree of freedom.

Table 2: Mean, Normality and Factor Loading

Items	Mean	SD	Skewness	kurtosis	Factor Loading
ED1	3.07	1.208	-.248	-1.081	.795
ED2	3.18	1.212	-.265	-1.013	.873
ED3	3.17	1.188	-.279	-1.008	.834
ED4	3.16	1.141	-.207	-.993	.779
TT1	3.27	1.196	-.385	-.958	.775
TT2	3.23	1.166	-.321	-.993	.749
TT3	3.22	1.160	-.286	-1.012	.807
TT4	3.31	1.104	-.307	-.965	.866
TT5	3.38	1.134	-.345	-.941	.838
TT6	3.39	1.093	-.370	-.846	.885
TT7	3.42	1.054	-.412	-.774	.838
FC1	3.45	1.287	-.502	-1.000	.842
FC2	3.38	1.302	-.402	-1.125	.853
FC3	3.43	1.271	-.424	-1.100	.837
FC4	3.50	1.234	-.501	-.961	.898
FC5	3.53	1.241	-.521	-.961	.911
FC6	3.50	1.251	-.477	-1.021	.902
FC7	3.51	1.249	-.495	-1.001	.939
FC8	3.51	1.239	-.491	-.968	.936
FC9	3.47	1.242	-.426	-1.037	.923
FC10	3.47	1.252	-.419	-1.093	.923
PI1	3.30	1.299	-.335	-1.128	.845
PI2	3.36	1.282	-.408	-1.045	.859
PI3	3.39	1.251	-.483	-.912	.844
MU1	3.43	1.306	-.391	-1.166	.829
MU2	3.48	1.291	-.412	-1.159	.851
MU3	3.55	1.245	-.478	-1.034	.878
MU4	3.60	1.216	-.627	-.777	.868

Table 2 is displaying means and skewness values that are indicators of descriptive statistics, it also exhibiting factor loading of each constructs along with it items. Constructs were tested by total 28 items, among which mean value of Environmental dynamism 4 items ED4 (3.16) and ED1(3.07), Technological turbulence TT7 (3.42) - TT1 (3.27) and product innovativeness PI3 (3.39) to PI1(3.30) is leaned towards 3.3 revealing that most of the participants gave neutral responses or agreed with the stated declaration. Whereas, internal locus of control and MAS information use average mean varies between 3.5 to 3.6 which is close to 4 which assumes that most of the respondents showed agreement. Additionally, Skewness values nor fall below -1 nor exceeds +1 which confirms data normality in distribution. Factor loading of all items is also plotted in last column which ranges from .749 to .936 that is greater than threshold 0.7 value which indicates no error of cross loading and high validity of data.

Table 3: Convergent and Discriminant Validity

	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	ED	TT	EF	MU	PI
ED	0.919	0.741	0.266	0.920	0.861				
TT	0.949	0.728	0.266	0.971	0.516	0.853			
EF	0.923	0.852	0.233	0.998	0.441	0.396	0.923		
MU	0.936	0.785	0.222	0.998	0.404	0.471	0.400	0.886	
PI	0.931	0.819	0.233	0.998	0.447	0.450	0.483	0.360	0.905

Similarly, Table 3 integrates Convergent validity and Discriminant Validity of this study by calculating composite reliability Average, Variance Extracted and discriminant validity of separate variable respectively. The environmental dynamism and technological turbulence has the minimum (0.919) and maximum (0.934) values of CR correspondingly. On other side, Product innovativeness encompasses highest value (0.819) and lowest value (0.728) of AVE. Since CR and AVE values for all variables are > 0.7 and >0.5, data is convergent valid. Values in diagonal form of table shows that each variable is more connected with itself as each of the values are larger than the values proceeded by them, confirming that discriminant validity exists in the data which shows difference existed between variables value.

Table 4: Model Fit Indices

Model Fit Indicators	CMIN/DF	GFI	IFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA
Threshold Value	≤ 3	≥ 0.80	≥ 0.90	≥ 0.90	≥ 0.90	≤ 0.08
Observed Value	2.773	0.878	0.967	0.963	0.967	0.061

Model fit indices in Table 4 test the research model fitness through CMIN/DF (discrepancy function) , GFI (goodness of fit index), CFI (comparative fit index) IFI (incremental fit index) and RMSEA. The observed values for are 2.773 for CMIN/DF, 0.878 for GFI, 0.967 for IFI, 0.963 for CFI and 0.061 for RMSEA. All these values are up to threshold values and validate that model has good fitness.

Figure 2: CFA

Table 5: Path Coefficient of SEM

	Ptah		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
TechTurb	<---	EnvDynsm	.452	.037	12.160	***
ProdInn	<---	EnvDynsm	.313	.052	6.035	***
ProdInn	<---	TechTurb	.351	.056	6.268	***
MASUse	<---	EnvDynsm	.182	.052	3.527	***
MASUse	<---	TechTurb	.369	.056	6.606	***
MASUse	<---	ProdInn	.132	.044	2.976	.003

Structural equation model was administered on AMOS to investigate hypothesis, results showed that all hypotheses have significant relationship therefore are accepted. It can be seen that increase of one unit in Environmental dynamism cause 45.2% increment in technology turbulence and 31.3% in product innovativeness, likewise Technology turbulence significantly impact product innovativeness because unitary addition in it will bring 35.1 % increase in MAS use of information. Results also show that product innovation increases MAS use of information by 13.2 percent and will have significant impact.

Table 6: Mediation and Moderation Effect

Hypothesis	B-Value	SE	P-Value
ED→TT→PI	.141	.021	.010
ED→TT→MAS	.21	.035	.010
TT*FC→PI	.003	.019	.747
TT*→FC-MAS	.328	.028	.010

Table 6 shows that, that increasing one unit in Environmental dynamism, technical turbulence and would increase product innovativeness by 14.1% and MAS info use by 21%,

moreover, technical turbulence and locus of control will upgrade product innovativeness and MAS info use by 0.3 % and 32.8% relatively. All p-values are less than 0.1 or 10% so it concluded that the all hypotheses are accepted except third.

Figure 3: SEM

Moderation

5. DISCUSSION

A study by Kamasak, Yozgat, and Yavuz (2017) illustrates that environmental dynamism can be used as an effective tool to enhance product innovation as well as the performance of the sector. The implementation of environmental dynamism practices can help to better brand innovation also improve the performance of the accounting system of the herbal sector of Thailand, and this also indicated by the first result of the hypothesis and hypothesis has been accepted. Environmental dynamism practices also have a huge impact on the product innovation process because ED can promote a system of innovation that is very helpful for product innovation (Chan, Yee, Dai, & Lim, 2016). Therefore, the second hypothesis of the research paper has been accepted. Technological turbulence plays a crucial mediating role in enhancing many relationships in the study and the hypothesis regarding TT has been accepted according to measurements of the results because TT can develop a system that changes the appearance of product and brand.

According to results the impact of ED and technological turbulence has been significant in the management accounting system used during the making of health drugs. This is because ED improved the management system of the firm with a competitive advantage and also improves the ability of the business. Therefore, the hypothesis regarding the impact of ED and TT on MAS usage has been accepted.

6. CONCLUSION

The significant aim of the study is to identify the impact of environmental dynamism on the management accounting systems and product innovation of the herbal firms of Thailand that generally produce health-related drugs. For this purpose, the study collects data mainly from about 471 employees of herbal firms out of which 262 were males and 209 were females. For the evaluation of collected data and information, the study used KMO, SEM and Bartlett's test.

6.1 Implications and Limitations

The following study will be very significant and helpful for the herbal firms of Thailand that produce health drug products and brands. The results of the study also help the herbal firms

that produce health drug products to improve the product innovation practices and also help them to effectively manage the accounting systems of the sector. The research also provides some significant data for future researchers to evaluate the innovation performance of herbal firms in Thailand in terms of their drug products. On the other hand, the study also has some limitations such as the study is limited to the mediating role of technological turbulence and also uses some specific methods to analyze the collected information. So, it is proposed to the future researchers and analysts that they should involve other mediating variables to identify the impact of environmental dynamism on the product innovation of herbal firms of Thailand. Furthermore, the analysts should other advance methods and tests to evaluate the data of the study.

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